

The Role of Mental Health on Examination Stress and Happiness on Under Graduate Students

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Abstract

In today's progressive are psychological research can be very helpful study the problems of society, social sciences like sociology, economics, psychology etc. Were used in various branches of psychology like child psychology, educational psychology and industrial psychology etc. We have to suffer many problems in this type of study. The main purpose of this research was to a study of the role of mental health on Examination Stress and happiness on Under Graduate students. The total sample consisted 100 as a variation belonging to 50 female and 50 male. The research tool for mental health measured by Virginia Dresch (2006) and tool for Examination Stress was measured by Ryff (2010) and tool for

happiness was measured by Lyubomirsky & Lepper (1999). To check the significant difference between group t-test was used here.

Keywords Examination Stress , Happiness

Introduction

The Role of Mental Health on Examination Stress and Happiness on Under Graduate Students

Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community. It is an integral component of health and well-being that underpins our individual and collective abilities to make decisions, build relationships and shape the world we live in. Mental health is a basic human right. And it is crucial to personal, community and socio-economic development.

Mental health is more than the absence of mental disorders. It exists on a complex continuum, which is experienced differently from one person to the next, with varying degrees of difficulty and distress and potentially very different social and clinical outcomes.

Exam stress is the feeling of tension and worry that comes from test-taking situations. It is normal to feel some stress about upcoming tests, exams, papers or presentations. Indeed, a small amount of stress can challenge you and stimulate you to work harder. Exam stress becomes problematic when it interferes with your ability to perform and achieve your academic and learning goals.

Signs and symptoms of exam stress

Below are some signs that indicate you may be experiencing exam stress:

Physical signs include a fast heartbeat, tense muscles, headache, sweating, upset stomach, nausea, diarrhea, dry mouth and difficulty sleeping.

Behavioural signs include fidgeting, nail biting, and increased smoking, drinking or eating.

Mental and emotional signs include difficulty concentrating, racing thoughts, "going blank," worry, and uncontrolled feelings of fear, dread or helplessness.

Happiness is an electrifying and elusive state. Feelings joyful has its health perks as well. A growing body of research also suggests that happiness can improve your physical health,

feelings oh positively and fulfillment seem to benefit cardiovascular health. The immune system, Inflammation levels and blood pressure, among others things happiness has even been linked to a longer lifespan as well as a higher quality of life and well -being.

Objective of study

The main objectives of study were as under :

1. To known the effect mental health on Examination Stress
2. To known the effect mental health on happiness.
3. To known the difference of mental health with reference to gender.

Review of Literature

Paul Ratanasiripong, T. China (2018) study result self – esteem, resiliency, and family economic status were significantly correlated with each of the mental health variable.

Sameera S. Rifqa A. N .(2015) finding reveled significant moderate positive correlation between happiness and mental health findings also indicated no significant gender differences in the level of happiness and mental health among youth morevos, social–demographics were found not to play and significant role among university students in this happiness and well-being.

Angela B. Gerrit H. (2019) The results show that the positive mental health and happiness scale are measurement invariantoves. Time and that the constructs are positively intes-related, but show different reciprocate patterns over time.

Gopal C. Ritika Y. (2015) results show that they enjoy both psychological physiological well- being. Happy people are also more sociable and enjoy quite good social well – being in this regard these people are healthier than to the unhappy people. Therefore different techniques have been used by psychologist and social scientist to make people healthier and ultimately healthy physically, socially and mentally..

Davosen M. Shiely F.(2013) results show that positive mental health and well- being scores in third level students sample using wemwrs. The findings suggest that students with a relatively adverse health and life style profile have higher than average mental health and social well-being.

Hypothesis

1. There will be no significance mental health on Examination stress.
2. There will be no significance mental health on happiness.

Methodology

According to the purpose of present study total 100 participants has been selected. There were 50 female and 50 male. Were taken as a sample from particular area of Surendranagar City (Gujarat).

Sampling

In this study random sampling method was used intial meeting with the participants was mode at particular areas of Amreli city (Gujarat). Total 100 participants were taken as a sample they were informed about the purpose of the study upon intiar meeting each participants was also explained the nature of the study participants were informed about the confidentiality regarding information collected from them. A time for data collection was set up that was conductive for the participants before administering the scale the purpose of the study was again explained to the participants. A good rapport was built with the participants for getting correct response some necessary instruction and guide lines were provided to them properly filling the scale afters this both scale were provided to them and they were requested to fill up the both scale after completion of the scale participants returned the scale and they were thanked for their participation and co-operation

Tools Used

Following instrument were used for data collection.

(A) Examination Stress Scale : The psychological well-being scale was developed by Goldberg & Williams (1988). This scale contains 12 items with 3 alternative response varying from strongly agree somewhat agree, A little agree, neither agree, somewhat agree, each to be rated on 3 point scale this scale interpretation can if higher scores mean higher levels of Examination Stress alpha coefficients reliability 0.92 and subscale 0.60 to 0.75 reliability.

(B) Happiness Scale : The happiness scale was developed by Lyubomirsky & Lepper (1999). The scale consisted of 4 items, each to be rated on 7 point scale test retest reliability 0.90 and validity 0.72.

Statistics Used in the Study

The main objective of present study was to measure Examination Stress and happiness in female and male. In it statistical t-test method is used.

Result and Discussion

The main objective of present study was to measure Examination Stress and happiness in female and male. In it statistical t-test method is used.

Table-1 Showing t-value score of Examination Stress in Male and Female.

Type Of Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig.
Male	100	2.52	2.45	3.7	0.01
Female	100	1.16	1.54		

Significant Level 0.05 = 2.00

0.01 = 2.66

According to test table of Examination Stress (table-1) showing t- value 3.6. The mean of male 2.40 and female mean 10.16. The standard deviation of male is 2.53 and female standard deviation is 2.32. The t- test value of significant difference at the both level (0.01 and 0.05 level). So we can say that one and two hypothesis is not accepted possible reason will be due to the long lasting pandemic situation and onerous measure such as lock down and study at home orders. The COVID – 19 pandemic brings negative impacts on Examination Stress in male and female.

Table-2 Showing t-value score of Happiness in Male and Female.

Type Of Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig.
Male	100	12.25	2.49	6.44	0.01
Female	100	10.13	2.36		

Significant Level 0.05 = 2.00

0.01 = 2.66

According to test table of happiness (table-2) showing t- value 6.45. The mean of male 12.23 and female mean 10.16. The standard deviation of male is 2.48 and female standard deviation is 2.32. The t- test value of significant difference at the both level (0.01 and 0.05 level). So we can say that one and two hypothesis is not accepted possible reason will be COVID-19 mental health effect on happiness is low correlation in female and male college students.

Conclusion

We can conclude by data analysis as follows :

There was significant difference in Examination Stress in male and female on mental health and there was significant difference on happiness in mental health.

Suggestions for the future Study

Endevour can be executed to analyze more than 60 data of sample with efficacy to attain better result for the accumulation of information, variegated methods except questionnaire can be adopted selection of sample can be accomplished with the intake of different city female and male people. Other method of selecting sample can be appropriated.

Limitation of the Study

The study had several limitation that can addressed by future research first the participants consists only particulars area of Amreli city. It is not representative of all their city. Hence, a more representative participants from different city of Gujarat might show significant interaction effect of differently.

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